
CTAO Instrument Response Functions: Comparison of prod5 and prod3b releases

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1 Introduction

The Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO) is the next-generation ground-based observatory designed to study the universe at gamma-ray energies above 20 GeV. CTAO will comprise two observatories, one in the Northern hemisphere (La Palma, Spain) and one in the Southern hemisphere (Paranal, Chile). It is set to surpass any existing gamma-ray detector with its exceptional angular resolution, sensitivity, and wide energy range. The recently concluded pre-construction phase of CTAO saw several evolutionary versions of the planned observatory. During pre-construction phase, the observatory's design changed continuously due to improvements of telescopes, detectors, changes following optimisation of the telescope layouts, and refined simulation and reconstruction algorithms. The introduction of the CTAO *Alpha* configuration for the installations freezes the number of telescopes and telescope types per observatory site for the first stage of CTAO construction.

The CTAO Instrument Response Functions (IRFs) are derived from detailed Monte Carlo simulations and describe the expected performance of the observatory. Detailed descriptions of the CTAO Monte Carlo simulations and instrument response functions and how they are calculated can be found in Refs. [7, 1, 2]. CTAO makes its instrument response functions available to the scientific community in different file formats through the Zenodo portal (*prod3b*: [5]; *prod5*: [6]).

CTAO recommends to use whenever possible the newest release of instrument response functions (*prod5*). These provide the most realistic estimates for the performance of the observatory.

This note compares the CTAO Instrument Response Functions between two design stages of CTAO captured by the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo simulation productions.

2 Evolution of the CTA Observatory and Monte Carlo models

The most significant changes between the Monte Carlo productions *prod3b*, published in 2016, and *prod5*, published in 2021 are:

1. Changes in detector design by the telescope teams affecting all aspects of the instrument (optics, camera, trigger, readout).
2. Optimized array configuration (number of telescopes) and array layouts (see below).
3. Updates to the simulation software and model; in particular an improved description of the telescopes and observation conditions by the telescope model as a result of tuning of the model parameters to measurements obtained in the laboratory or with prototypes. Telescope models are published and available for both *prod3b* [4] and *prod5* [3].
4. Improved reconstruction and background suppression methods (using the Eventdisplay package [10] version 5.0.0 [8] for *prod3b* vs 5.4.0 [9] for *prod5*).¹
5. Refined description of atmospheric and geomagnetic field models.

The most notable changes between Monte Carlo productions *prod3b* and *prod5* are the number of telescopes per site and the corresponding optimized array layouts (see Figures 1 and 2). The *prod3b*

¹The CTAO reconstruction software is currently under development and is expected to provide notable improvements in reconstruction quality.

Figure 1 – Telescope layouts for the CTAO northern (left) southern (right) site as used for the calculation of the *prod3b* instrument response functions. Telescope types are indicated in the legend (LST: large-size telescope, MST: mid-size telescope, SST: small-size telescope).

Figure 2 – Telescope layouts for the CTAO northern (left) southern (right) site as used for the calculation of the *prod5* instrument response functions. Telescope types are indicated in the legend (LST: large-size telescope, MST: mid-size telescope, SST: small-size telescope). These layouts correspond to the Alpha configuration to be built on both sites during the construction phase.

layout configuration for the CTAO Northern Site consisted of 4 LSTs and 15 MSTs, while the *prod5* Alpha configuration consists of 4 LSTs and 9 MSTs and corresponding changes the array layout. For the Southern site, *prod3b* included 4 LSTs, 25 MSTs, and 70 SSTs, while *prod5* Alpha consists of 14 MSTs and 37 SSTs. Note that the reduced number of telescopes for the Alpha configuration of *prod5* compared to *prod3b* motivated by the available funding is at least partly offset by improvements in telescopes, detectors, layouts, and reconstruction software.

3 Comparison of *prod3b* vs *prod5* Instrument Response Functions

The figures below compare the differential flux sensitivities, angular resolutions, energy resolutions and effective areas derived from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions. For a detailed definition of the parameters plotted, see e.g. the CTAO performance website² or Ref. [6]. In short, the definitions are as follows:

²<https://www.cta-observatory.org/science/ctao-performance/>

- the differential flux sensitivity is defined as the minimum flux needed by CTAO to obtain a 5-standard-deviation detection of a point-like source, calculated in non-overlapping logarithmic energy bins (five bins per decade). Besides the significant detection requirement, at least ten detected gamma rays per energy bin and a signal/background ratio of at least 1/20 are required.
- The angular resolution in each energy bin is defined as the angle containing 68% of the reconstructed gamma-ray events relative to the simulated gamma-ray direction.
- The energy resolution $\Delta E/E$ is obtained from the distribution of $(E_R - E_T) / E_T$, where R and T refer to the reconstructed and true energies of gamma-ray events recorded by CTAO. $\Delta E/E$ is the half-width of the interval around 0 which contains 68% of the distribution.

Figure 3 – Comparison between the differential flux sensitivity of the CTAO Southern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming an observation time of 50 h and point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 20 deg, averaged over azimuth directions. The sensitivity is shown for gamma-ray sources located on-axis and at 3 deg offset to the camera centre.

Figure 4 – Comparison between the differential flux sensitivity of the CTAO Southern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming an observation time of 50 h and point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 40 deg, averaged over azimuth directions. The sensitivity is shown for gamma-ray sources located on-axis and at 3 deg offset to the camera centre.

Figure 5 – Comparison between the differential flux sensitivity of the CTAO Southern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming an observation time of 50 h and point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 60 deg, averaged over azimuth directions. The sensitivity is shown for gamma-ray sources located on-axis and at 3 deg offset to the camera centre.

Figure 6 – Comparison between the angular resolution (left) and energy resolution (right) of the CTAO Southern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming on-axis point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 20 deg. The angular resolution and energy resolution are plotted as a function of reconstructed energy calculated for gamma-hadron separation cuts optimized for 50h of observations.

Figure 7 – Comparison between the differential flux sensitivity of the CTAO Northern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming an observation time of 50 h and point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 20 deg, averaged over azimuth directions. The sensitivity is shown for gamma-ray sources located on-axis and at 3 deg offset to the camera centre.

Figure 8 – Comparison between the differential flux sensitivity of the CTAO Northern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming an observation time of 50 h and point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 40 deg, averaged over azimuth directions. The sensitivity is shown for gamma-ray sources located on-axis and at 3 deg offset to the camera centre.

Figure 9 – Comparison between the differential flux sensitivity of the CTAO Northern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming an observation time of 50 h and point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 60 deg, averaged over azimuth directions. The sensitivity is shown for gamma-ray sources located on-axis and at 3 deg offset to the camera centre.

Figure 10 – Comparison between the angular resolution (left) and energy resolution (right) of the CTAO Northern Site as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions assuming on-axis point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 20 deg. The angular resolution and energy resolution are plotted as a function of reconstructed energy calculated for gamma-hadron separation cuts optimized for 50h of observations.

Figure 11 – Comparison between the effective areas as obtained from the *prod3b* and *prod5* Monte Carlo productions for the CTAO Southern Site (left) and the CTAO Northern Site (right) assuming on-axis point-like gamma-ray sources at a zenith distance of 20 deg. The effective area is shown as a function of true energy and was obtained applying cuts optimized for 30 min observation time.

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